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**Integration of land use vector data from administrative sources
for agri-environmental analysis.**

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Abbreviations:

AGEA	<i>Agenzia per le erogazioni in agricoltura</i>
Cas	Numerical identifier that uniquely identifies a chemical substance
CREA	<i>Consiglio per la Ricerca in agricoltura e l'analisi dell'economia agraria</i> , Italian research organization dedicated to the agri-food supply chains
DEM	Digital Elevation Model
EFA	Ecological Focus Area
FA	<i>Fascicolo Aziendale</i> , Company File
IACS	Integrated Administration and Control System
ISPRA	<i>Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale</i> , The Italian Institute for Environmental Protection and Research
LISP	Land Parcel Information System, AGEA database of polygon, lines or points containing information about land use and land coverage.
RF	Refresh Layer
SIAN	<i>Sistema Informativo Agricolo Nazionale</i>

Definitions:

Copernicus Sentinel-2 mission comprises a constellation of two polar-orbiting satellites placed in the same sun-synchronous orbit, phased at 180° to each other. It aims at monitoring variability in land surface conditions, and its wide swath width and high revisit will support monitoring of Earth's surface changes (The European Space Agency, n.d.).

Corine Land Cover is an inventory of land cover in 44 classes for the European region (CORINE Land Cover, s.d.).

Digital Elevation Model (DEM) is a 3D approximation of the terrain's surface created from elevation data.

IACS (European Commission, s.d.) consists of a number of digital and interconnected databases, in particular:

- a system for the identification of all agricultural plots in EU countries, called the land parcel identification system;
- a system allowing farmers to graphically indicate the agricultural areas for which they apply for aid (the geospatial aid application);
- a computerised database for animals in EU countries where animal-based aid schemes apply;
- an integrated control system which ensures systematic checks of aid applications based on computerised cross checks and physical on-farm controls (on-the spot checks).

Vector layer/layers data provide a way to represent real world features within the GIS environment. A feature is anything you can see on the landscape.

Abstract:

The use of georeferenced data for monitoring and supporting agricultural policies has been a common practice for many years. However, these administrative data sources can find additional uses in other research fields. This study aims to examine administrative data sources of land use and land coverage, obtained through the European Open IACS project, describing their strengths and limitations. Then this study suggests a methodological process for their integration and use in statistical analysis. Through Correspondence Analysis, I study the association between land use with the presence of Isoproturon, a plant protection product, in the surface waters of the Italian province of Foggia.

Keywords: Open IACS, administrative data, GIS, land-use, land-cover, DEM, Correspondence Analysis, plant protection product

Introduction:

In this thesis, I want to analyze some aspects of the Italian case study in the EU Project Open IACS.

Open IACS (CREA, s.d.) is a technological project focused on the use/reuse of data from the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP), improving access and usability for different categories of users. These datasets are stored in the LPIS database from AGEA. In Italy, CREA with the collaboration of AGEA, ISPRA and ENEA, is developing a platform that, by exploiting the integration of data sources (Linked Open Data) and the use of High-Performance Computing (HPC), facilitates the calculation of indicators and the provision of services. The objective is to harmonize and make available in open format, data from administrative registers (AGEA) and environmental datasets (ISPRA).

The project Open IACS allows the use of administrative data provided by the Institution that participate in it. In particular, AGEA manages the information regarding crop declaration (IACS) and other georeferenced dataset that are used for monitoring land use in Italy. In this thesis I describe these datasets, their opportunities and limitations explaining why their joint use should be preferred. After describing a methodology for their merge, I will show a case study that analyses the possible correlation between land use and the presence of chemicals in surface water for the province of Foggia.

Data:

The datasets, provided by AGEA, contain information regarding land use for the Italian region Puglia. The AGEA datasets are organized in vector layers that divide the land in polygons. Each polygon is associated with specific codes that allow to identify characteristics such as type of land use, the municipal and other details. The ISPRA dataset on the other hand is formed by point in the region Puglia with surveys of the concentration of chemicals in surface water. The original spatial reference of these layers is the Gauss Boaga but in the elaboration process, it is converted to the more widely used WSG 84 / 32N. The conversion is not straightforward and can cause a shift in the position of the polygon making it more difficult to confront multiple layers (see Figure 1¹).

Figure 1

¹ Figure 1: Orthophotos in the background, FA continued lines, RF dotted lines. There is no correspondence between the borders of the polygons of the two layers and the orthophotos.

The analysis of the layers is done with Arcgis software using the WSG 84 / 32N reference system.

Refresh:

The Refresh layer, developed by SIAN on behalf of AGEA, consists of a complete mapping of the Italian territory through the interpretation of orthophotos (see Figure 2²) (SIAN, 2016).

This layer is used during the procedure for assigning European funds to agriculture: it provides a certified basis on which farmers can create their own declarations.

The update of this base has a three-year term. Italy is divided into 3 macro-areas and one every year is updated (see Figure 3³).

Figure 3

Figure 2

The photo-interpretation methodology adopted provides the complete delimitation of parcels (intended as continuous portions of land with homogeneous land cover/use) regardless of the land registry boundaries and the territorial consistency of the companies registered in the SIAN registry.

The interpretation process starts from the previous Refresh layer, which is updated using the new orthophotos. This procedure is necessary to guarantee a fundamental distinction between real variations of the territory and false ones due to changes in the acquisition process; an example can be found in the improvement of the resolution of the pixel reached 20cm which can cause apparent variations in land use. To obtain a coherent geometric layer between refresh and orthophoto, a calibration process is performed which consists in shifting the polygons. This procedure guarantees consistency with past data but complicates the comparison with other data sources as it can generate a misalignment between spatial references (SIAN, 2016).

The data is structured in polygons which are associated with administrative information such as regional, provincial, municipal and cadastral codes as well as a numerical code that

² Figure 2: Example of the photo interpretation process (SIAN, 2016).

³ Figure 3: The subdivision of Italy for the update of Refresh (SIAN, 2016).

identifies the type of land occupation. The coding tables are provided by SIAN and a description can be found in the published attachments with vector data.

The dataset used in this analysis refers to the 2016 survey of Foggia province.

Fascicolo Aziendale:

The Fascicolo Aziendale is a vector layer that refers to the data of the farmers' declarations to access European funds.

These declarations are submitted every year by farmers through an online platform that allows to identify their parcels on the map and assign information on the land use. The polygons initially refer to the cadaster data, with the consequent problems of reliability and updating times. To overcome this problem, farmers can autonomously update the borders. As it is not mandatory, the update of the polygons is not always carried out.

This vector layer includes only the agricultural areas for which a declaration has been made, and as a result, a large part of the territory is not represented. The disadvantage of territorial coverage is far outweighed by the high detail of the land use data. The codes, in fact, consist of four levels that identify land occupation (grain, vines ...), intended use (forage, industry ...), description of use and description of quality. These codes have a level of detail far superior to that of the refresh and allow the identification of specific land use such as EFAs.

The dataset used in this analysis refers to the 2018 survey of the Foggia province.

GIS Suolo:

This layer can be described as an “intersection” between Fascicolo Aziendale and Refresh as it uses the same reference system as the Fascicolo Aziendale but the Refresh coding system. GIS Suolo is generated annually by AGEA using its own administrative procedures, such as objective checks on land use declarations or reviews.

The correspondence between its polygons and those of Fascicolo Aziendale allows an almost perfect overlap when both are present (see Figure 4⁴); moreover, unlike the Fascicolo Aziendale, any drawing errors or similar can be corrected by the photo interpreter during the elaboration process.

Figure 4

⁴ Figure 4: The marked black line is the FA while the gray transparent area is GIS Suolo. The polygons have the same coordinates.

The use of refresh codes combined with control information allows for better identification of land use; for example, in the case of code 430, citrus tree, it is possible to identify whether it is orange, clementine or others.

The GIS Suolo, like Fascicolo Aziendale, does not cover the entire land surface.

The dataset used in this analysis refers to the 2018 surveys of the Foggia province.

Chemicals:

The data regarding the presence of chemicals in surface-waters in the Puglia region were provided by ISPRA and refer to the report on pesticides over the years 2015-2016 (ISPRA, 2018).

The dataset can be divided into two parts. The first one is the registry of the stations containing the coordinates of the survey points with the administrative information regarding the region and municipality; the identification of the monitoring station with the type; finally, information on the substances traced. The second part, instead, contains the analytical determinations carried out such as, for example, the substance sought, the number of positive detections, the total and average concentration.

This report uses data provided by the Italian regions that follow different sample designs for different water bodies, therefore there is no common framework neither for the spatial distribution of the survey stations nor for the number of chemicals to track.

Compared to the other regions in the report, in 2015-2016, Puglia tracks the lowest number of substances in surface waters (28 vs 186 in Sicily, 167 in Bolzano, 113 in Tuscany ...), and despite the fact that the number of stations in absolute terms is high, 59, it is not sufficient to cover the regional surface in a detailed way, making an extended analysis complicated ($3,0 \text{ stations/km}^2 \times 10^3$).

The monitoring stations are unevenly distributed throughout the provincial territory as 37 are located in the province of Foggia alone and seems to be clustered around certain area of interest (there are about $0.005 \text{ stations / km}^2$ against a national average of $5.4 \text{ stations / km}^2$) (see Figure 5⁵).

Among these 28 substances studied, I decided to analyze the presence of Isoproturon (cas 34123-59-6), a plant protection product used as an herbicide in agriculture.

⁵ Figure 5: The red dots represent the location of the survey stations.

Figure 5

Multiple Data Sources:

The use of Refresh alone as a data source to carry out studies and calculate indicators of interest has the advantage of having a total coverage of the land use but the long updating period and the lack of a high level of detail can limit quality and scope. In fact, in the Refresh there is a lack of information on the land left to rest, on the areas withdrawn from production or on the areas of ecological interest.

The employment of auxiliary data, already in use within AGEA, can improve and expand this type of research. In fact, even if they do not cover the whole territory, the data within GIS Suolo and Fascicolo Aziendale are updated annually and contain more detailed information.

In this chapter I confront the different layers and explain how to fix their topology and geometry problems and a possible way to combine them into one layer

Comparison:

Before proceeding with the union of the layers, it is necessary to think about the two types of coding present in the data. The codes that identify land use in GIS Suolo are the same as Refresh and although some may be similar to the Fascicolo Aziendale, they do not always identify the same type of use. It is therefore optimal to try to preserve the two encodings separately, so that it can be possible to use the most appropriate one during the analysis. Since the encoding of Refresh and GIS is available throughout the territory, the aggregation of these two layers is easier than a direct confrontation with Fascicolo Aziendale.

It is also necessary to impose a hierarchy on the three layers based on their reliability. The Fascicolo Aziendale is considered the reference layer, as it is updated more often and has the most rigorous controls; then, GIS Suolo and finally Refresh.

While the Fascicolo Aziendale and the GIS Suolo have the same spatial references and the polygons usually coincide, the Refresh polygons tend to remain shifted respect to the others. This problem complicates the joining process as it would lead to the creation of sliver polygons⁶ with areas close to zero which weigh down the processes and worsen the quality of the data.

The problem of small polygons is present in all three layers. The technical specifications do not provide for a resolution method or a minimum area for which a polygon can be represented. To reduce their number, the tolerance for XY coordinates was set to 0.1m and polygons with an area less than 1sqm were absorbed in the bordering polygon with the largest area.

Example of checking and fixing topology and geometry problems in the Refresh layer: On the first import of RF Layer for Puglia there are 225 977 polygons of which 31 596 have an area smaller than 1sqm. After setting the tolerance and resolution level of XY to 0.1m and running a *repair geometry* 193 660 Polygons remained (only 180 with area smaller than 1smq).

Now it is possible to proceed with the creation of a topology, the arrangement that defines how point, line, and polygon features share coincident geometry. The rules are:

- The refresh layer must not have gaps.
- Features must not overlap.
- Features must be larger than cluster tolerance (0.1m).

The results are that 7 polygons are smaller than 0.1m; there are 2 100 gaps in the layer and 413 overlaps. After fixing these issues, I proceeded with an *Eliminate* that absorbs the selected polygon (those created for filling the gaps and those with area less than 1sqm) in the bordering polygon with the largest area.

The new layer has 193 484 features. The last part is to run the command *Dissolve Boundaries* that finds polygons that overlap or share a common boundary and merges them together to form a single polygon.

The final layer has 181 834 polygons, a reduction of 19.5% with only 68 polygons with area less than 1smq that can only be fixed manually.

This kind of error are non-statistical ones, therefore, should not be used to make assumption about any other layer. The results for the RF cannot be used to evaluate the number of errors present in FA or GIS Suolo.

⁶ Polygon slivers can occur during extraction when small, thin polygons are accidentally created through an overlap with existing features.

Methodology:

In order to proceed with the merge of the different layers, it is necessary to address the problems of overlapping perimeters, null areas, polygons with less than three vertices and, in the case of the refresh, empty areas.

The process of joining the layers is quite linear. The Refresh was used to fill in the voids of GIS Suolo therefore have a complete coverage of the territory. It should be noted that the areas not covered by GIS Suolo are mostly roads, cities and uncultivated areas which therefore tend to remain unchanged in the period of three years.

The Fascicolo Aziendale is overlaid on this layer. Having checked and solved the errors that are generated by the union of georeferenced layers with different coordinate systems, it is necessary to check that there is a correspondence between the two land use code systems.

Starting from the comparison tables provided by AGEA, I added the combinations of codes from the Fascicolo Aziendale and GIS Suolo / Refresh and to each I assigned the value 0 or 1 based on the correspondence. Since the descriptions of the codes do not clarify in detail what they can be associated with, it must be made clear that this value 0-1 is not to be considered as an absolute, it does not indicate an error, but a situation of uncertainty that must be checked.

Once the polygons with correspondence problems have been identified, for each one the polygon of the reference Fascicolo Aziendale has been identified with correspondence = 1 and greater area. The latter's GIS/RF code was used to overwrite the problematic one.

Analytic Description:

Considering the province of Foggia, we have 181 834 polygons in Refresh layer, in GIS Suolo 482 616 while in FA 427 794. It can be seen that Refresh, which has complete land coverage, has the least number of polygons whose associated areas are larger than the other two layers. Gis Suolo and Fascicolo Aziendale, on the other hand, have more polygons but their number are similar.

Proceeding with the union of GIS Soil and Refresh we obtain a layer of 580 559 polygons that has total land coverage. Once we add FA we get the new hybrid layer with 950 952 polygons

Observations:

This final layer is not exempt from issues.

The quality of the data depends on sources that use different procedures and methodologies; any error present in the original layers is difficult to account for in the new one due to the aggregation procedure. It is possible to correct codes regarding the use of soil once identified the parcel but changing geometries of the polygon is more challenging.

The use of two different set of coding that are not interchangeable and can slow down the analysis process. Also, Fascicolo Aziendale has many more identifications increasing the

possible combinations of the two sets. It would be difficult to change the methodologies behind how these layers are created. A special focus should be put on the definition that allows to classify specific land use: as there is not a perfect correspondence between the definitions, the uncertainties generated should be managed.

One other limitation is the computational power required to elaborate these layers. While the process of multiple union can be executed in a reasonable amount of time, checking and fixing topography error is a more strenuous task and demand more performing hardware. This limitation can also be noticed in software that are not optimized for multi-core processors.

These problems should not restrain from using this new hybrid layer. In fact, a more common use of these data sources outside their first purpose will lead to a progressive improvement in quality such as the creation of rules to address the conflicts between codes and the creation of a minimal identifiable area for each land use to avoid of small polygons. Fixed the initial problems of the dataset, the use of double codes will not impact greatly on performance. Also, the development of specific algorithms would ease up these processes or it is always possible to split the area of interest in smaller sets and then aggregate.

At the moment, the procedure for switching to rasters is the only way to reduce the problems reported above.

Rasterization:

A raster consists of a matrix of cells (or pixels) organized into rows and columns (or a grid) where each cell contains a value representing information, such as temperature. Rasters are digital aerial photographs, imagery from satellites, digital pictures, or even scanned maps (ArcGIS, s.d.).

For the creation of the grid, I decided to use Sentinel data as Snap Raster⁷ so that the output raster matches its cell alignment. This is necessary to guarantee the same reference system in case its required to add them as a data source.

The Copernicus pixels have a resolution of 10mx10m which cover an area of 100sqm. Having to structure an analysis on the chemicals present in the water, it is not necessary to consider pixels of smaller sizes and this resolution may already be too detailed. Since the area of interest remains limited to the province of Foggia, it is computationally feasible to maintain a 10x10 grid.

⁷ Snap Raster: Arcgis calls the reference raster snap raster

Analysis:

Chemicals:

Data relating to chemicals substances are represented with dots. The concentration levels of the substances detected are associated with each point. I decided to investigate the presence of ISOPROTURON (Cas 34123-59-6) in the waters, an herbicide included among the substances monitored by the European Union (ISPRA, 2018).

This plant protection product is found mostly in water (92.92%) and has a halving time between six and twenty-eight days (ISPRA).

The total concentration levels in the province of Foggia assume seven values with this frequency (Table 1):

Table 1

Province	Foggia
Chemical	Isoproturon
Level of concentration	Frequency
0,03	1
0,05	1
0,07	6
0,1	1
0,15	4
0,17	1
0,2	24
Total	38

Considering the type of data and the low number of surveys on the territory that tend to be concentrated in certain locations, using methods such as IDW to extend the surveys to the entire province would not lead to optimal results.

IDW is an acronym for Inverse Distance Weighted interpolation. this process is stored in raster and uses a lineary weighted combination of multiple points to determine the value of the raster. The assumption underneath is that the value of the variable being mapped decreased its influence as the distance increases. IDW gives good results when there are numerous points close to each other, a situation that is very far from this province reality as the stations are very far from each other and do not provide a full coverage of the land (ArcGIS, s.d.).

I found it more reliable to create a circular buffer with a distance of 5km and assume that the values measured in the station are extendable to the surrounding area. In case of nearby stations where buffers overlap, a boundary is created that evenly distributes the area of

intersection between polygons (see Figure 6⁸) (this methodology was also applied in this study: (Juan Antonio Pascual Aguilar, 2017)).

Figure 7

In order to refine this analysis, the use of the water basins could provide additional information. Their graphic representation is not available therefore by using Arcgis

Figure 6

⁸ Figure 6: The blue area represents the buffer where the level of concentration is assumed constant.

Hydrology commands I created them. For the input data I used a clipped portion of the Italian DEM⁹ raster available online.

As a result, it is possible to identify two main areas that are not connected (see Figure 7¹⁰)

The survey stations in the larger pink area refer mostly to rivers while the one in the dark blue are located in lagoon areas that follow different type of propagation of this type of chemical.

In the analysis, I will focus only on the stations located in the larger river basin. The number of survey station is 27 and the frequency for the level of concentration 0.03, 0.05, 0.1, 0.15, 0.17, 0.2 are respectively 1, 1, 1, 3, 1 and 20.

Correspondence Analysis:

Theory:

Correspondence analysis is an extension of Principle component analysis. In fact, while with PCA we can study continuous variable, CA provides the methods for exploring and describing the frequency of categorical variables in a contingency table. The idea behind it is to measure the dissimilarity between the rows and columns through the chi-squared distance. By doing so CA does not assume any type of distribution for the probability of the frequencies and allows to remove the structure inherent in the data. For this reason, the matrix cells should not contain negative values.

Correspondence analysis can be used for representing the categorical variables in a subspace of low dimensionality but not for hypothesis testing or evaluate the if the relationship between variables is statistically significant.

The methodologies behind CA are well described by Beh (Beh, 2004) and Greenacre (Greenacre, 2007).

CA uses the Single Values Decomposition of the frequency matrix to calculate its eigenvector and eigenvalues. The first obtained result is a measure of the difference, called Inertia that is the chi-square statistic divided by the total sample size: $\varphi^2 = \chi^2/N$. It has been proven that this measurement is also obtained by summing the eigenvalues of the decomposition; each eigenvalue is the measure of the inertia traceable to its dimension. For an $r \times c$ table, the maximum number of dimensions is $\min(r-1, c-1)$. The analysis is conducted only on a subset space chosen by the first k dimension which cumulatively exceed a threshold of explained inertia. The choice of the threshold is very important because adding more dimension can reduce the ability of providing a good interpretation.

The SVD provide also the principal coordinates that allow a graphical representation of the data structure. The combinations of the categorical variables can be represented as cloud of points in a low-dimension Cartesian space. The origin of the axes is the average row or column profile and the distance from it to a point describe the variation or the similarity

⁹ DEM: resolution of 20meters on a scale from 0 to 32767

¹⁰ Figure 7: Map in Arcgis where the blue and pink polygon represents the water basins, the lines the river, the dots the survey station and the black lines the province boundaries.

within the table. Points close to it means that the expected difference under the independence assumptions is small and clustered ones tend to have similar profiles.

The distance between rows and columns cannot be interpreted because it does not represent a defined quantity.

In the output of CA, with the graphic representation and information of the inertias there is a table with the details for each row and column. The mass is the proportion of observation for that point (row/column total divided by the sample size); the inertia is the contribution to the overall inertia; the correlation explains the part of the variation associated with the dimension; the quality is a value between 0 and 1 and shows how good each point is represented in the subspace (the higher the better); the absolute contribution explains how much of the inertia associated with the axis is attributable to the point.

Data:

The analysis dataset considers the hybrid raster created with the administrative data of land use associated with the concentration level of Isoproturon within the buffer zone.

The result is then exported in the form of points (15 772 668) and analyzed via R.

They are reorganized in the form of a table (735x7) in which the identification codes of the land use are in the rows, the concentration levels in the columns. Given the large number of land uses, it is necessary to reduce the number by aggregating them. First, I kept only the first two levels of the company file, reducing them to 630; so, I decided on a threshold level of 50,000 observations to be included in the analysis and aggregating them in 26 levels. I kept 13 584 287 (86,1%) of my initial points.

The total concentration can assume 5 values that are rounded at the second decimal position. These numbers do not seem to be originated from a continuous space but are more likely to be rounded. For this reason, I decided to interpret them as an ordered categorical variable and not a continuous one.

The table below (Table_2) represents the frequencies of land use sorted by the total concentration of Isoproturon detected in the river basin. The *chi-square* statistic for this table is 1331262 with 125 *df* and *p_value* = 0 therefore it is safe to assume some degree of association between these two categorical variables. The total inertia, computed as $\varphi^2 = \chi^2/N$, that describe the variation in the contingency table is: 0.098

Table 2

Land Use		Concentration					
Codi_conc_aggr ¹¹	Description	0.03	0.05	0.1	0.15	0.17	0.2
134-0	Tomato	270	356	6074	35139	32406	399234
2-0	Durum Wheat (Wheat)	19052	209230	101285	690535	240593	4324343
214-0	Agricultural Area Withdrawn From Production	5331	9261	13804	41170	20168	221668
214-14	Agricultural Area Withdrawn From Production Efa	4797	9947	13216	22405	23409	260750
300	Deciduous Woods	0	1043	0	3865	0	61085
316	Residential Urban Fabric	503	430	1231	1163	0	53015
318	Isolated Buildings	834	2794	358	10553	994	56851
320	Industrial And Commercial Areas	13	51	31	7721	598	47360
321	Transport Infrastructure	650	3758	1464	14843	3451	77965
330	Lakes And Water Basins Of Significant Surface	0	0	0	68806	0	2468
410-0	Vineyard	10806	3527	31823	60069	0	291991
420-0	Olive	574	4771	14238	93917	12165	499335
533-0	Oats	0	20296	765	24455	24355	222919
544-0	Chickpea	0	4101	2677	31924	5894	258192
544-111	Chickpea Efa	0	424	1417	15022	5605	107390
575-0	Beans	1659	2156	4401	16750	13580	111113
575-111	Beans Efa	504	8315	3102	18916	21248	108388
638-0	Polifita Pasture	4456	12049	7992	22084	14590	382899
651	Specialized Tree Cultivations Not Specified	2757	429	2737	15916	684	73024
654-0	Pascolo Arborato (Bosco Ceduo) Tare 50%	0	135	328	23	0	56333
660	Generic Building - Road	1807	4724	3131	65970	8723	252847
666	Seminative By Photo-Interpretation	78070	59532	32364	229206	52983	1599002
690	Waters	12888	4661	7616	43259	21730	253520
800-0	Grass	0	4580	0	7736	10517	153075
870-0	Barley	7012	27542	11083	67482	86800	443789
902-0	Asparagus	1154	0	547	18857	37738	190781

¹¹ Codi_conc_aggr is the aggregated code that identifies the land use. Basically the codes from RF and FA with the same description have been merged

Results:

The results from the ca package are reported in the tables below:

Table 3

Dimension	Principal Inertia	%	Cumulative%	Scree Plot
1	0.044321	45.2	45.2	*****
2	0.024759	25.3	70.5	*****
3	0.014939	15.2	85.7	****
4	0.007764	7.9	93.7	**
5	0.006217	6.3	100.0	**
Total:	0.098000	100.0		

In Table 3 are reported the level of inertia associated with each dimension. The use of the first two dimensions explains 70.5% of inertia, adding the third and fourth dimension would amount to 93.7% but it would complicate too much the analysis. For this reason, only the first and second dimensions will be considered.

Figure 8

The symmetric map of Figure 8 is a graphic visualization of the coordinates obtained from the frequency table.

Table 4 is the summary for the Rows (Land Use) while Table 5 for the Columns (Concentration of Isoproturon):

The values are multiplied by 1000.

Table 4

Code	Land Use	Mass	Quality	Inertia	Dimension 1			Dimension 2		
					Coordinates	Squared Correlation	Absolute contribution	Coordinates	Squared Correlation	Absolute contribution
134-0	Tomato	35	416	26	-160	350	20	-70	66	7
2-0	Durum Wheat	411	144	35	9	11	1	-34	133	19
214-0	Agricultural Area Withdrawn from Production	23	41	11	41	34	1	-19	7	0
214-14	Agricultural Area Withdrawn from Production EFA	25	470	14	-163	468	15	-9	2	0
300	Deciduous Woods	5	373	7	-161	180	3	167	193	5
316	Residential Urban Fabric	4	774	8	-257	362	6	274	412	13
318	Isolated Buildings	5	352	2	95	209	1	79	143	1
320	Industrial and Commercial Areas	4	133	4	71	53	0	87	80	1
321	Transport Infrastructure	8	446	1	81	444	1	-5	2	0
330	Lakes and Water Basins of Significant Surface	5	996	363	2553	961	771	-482	34	49
410-0	Vineyard	29	504	85	176	109	21	335	395	133
420-0	Olive Trees	46	346	24	112	249	13	70	97	9
533-0	Oats	22	655	27	-156	203	12	-234	452	48
544-0	Chickpea	22	122	12	-31	19	0	73	103	5
544-111	Chickpea EFA	10	10	4	-17	7	0	-11	3	0
575-0	Beans	11	362	6	-52	48	1	-132	314	8
575-111	Beans EFA	12	830	23	-80	34	2	-391	796	73
638-0	Polifita Pasture	33	898	19	-200	714	29	101	184	14
651	Specialized Tree Cultivations Not Specified	7	876	8	188	337	6	238	539	16
654-0	Pascolo Arborato (Bosco Ceduo) Tare 50%	4	603	12	-331	401	10	234	202	9
660	Generic Building - Road	25	752	19	236	752	31	5	0	0
666	Seminative By Photointerpretation	151	528	115	3	0	0	198	528	240
690	Waters	25	67	20	20	5	0	69	62	5
800-0	Grassland	13	727	12	-254	683	19	-65	45	2
870-0	Barley	47	745	88	-118	77	15	-349	668	233
902-0	Asparagus	18	678	56	-227	173	21	-387	504	111

Table 5

Concentration	Mass	Quality	Inertia	Dimension 1			Dimension2		
				Coordinates	Squared Correlation	Absolute contribution	Coordinates	Squared Correlation	Absolute contribution
0,03	11	353	167	28	1	0	715	353	233
0,05	29	136	70	-88	33	5	-156	103	29
0,1	19	149	89	56	7	1	253	142	50
0,15	120	999	390	559	979	845	-80	20	31
0,17	47	829	221	-240	124	61	-570	704	617
0,2	774	798	62	-71	632	87	36	166	41

Starting the analysis by studying Figure 8 we observe that many points are clustered in the origin of the axes, therefore, they are close to the average profile.

For the rows, (Table 4) there is a lot of diversity in the quality parameter: 330-Lakes and Water Basins Of Significant Surface is very well represented, as well as Beans EFA, as well as polyphite pastures and unspecified tree crops. On the contrary, chickpeas (544, EFA and not), small water surfaces (690) and Agricultural Area Withdrawn from Production (214) are not well explained by the two dimensions alone. This means that the level of concentration does not adequately represent changes in this type of land use and the quality of the chemical data should probably be improved.

Considering now the EFA-type areas, we have three types of land uses that also have this intended use. While some have low quality levels, their pairs are spaced apart. This shows that the establishment of this type of area could lead to a change in the use of plant protection products (in this case, isoproturon).

Lakes and Water Basins of Significant Surface (330) have an unusual behavior as they are the furthest from all points and are the best represented. They are also associated with the highest inertia. This distance confirms the hypothesis that large water basins have a different

behavior than other land uses regarding the concentration of isoproturon (and probably other chemicals).

As regards permanent tree, it does not seem to be much difference between the behavior of *Specialized Tree Cultivations Not Specified* and *Vineyards* (651 -410). On the other hand *Olive Trees* (420) are located more distant and closer to the origin of the axes.

We can see that the very common *Durum Wheat* (2-0) with the highest mass value, is very close to the origin of the axes and has a low quality of representation.

Regarding the squared correlation coefficient, it seems that considered crops do not have a strong correlation with the first principal axis while they show a stronger correlation with the second one. The opposite occurs if we consider buildings and infrastructure, which have a stronger correlation with the first axis than with the second. This type of relation is particularly evident once we take into consideration the value of the absolute contribution. For the first axis *Lakes and Water Basins of Significant Surface* (330) contributes to explanation of inertia for 77.1%. In the second dimension *Vineyard* (410), *Seminative By Photointerpretation* (666), *Barley* (870) and *Asparagus* (902) bring a greater contribution.

Considering now the columns, Table 5, we observe that the points are distant from each other and do not arrange themselves following a precise design. The quality levels are different, the higher concentrations are better represented (probably given the greater sample size) as opposed to the lower ones. It is noted that the highest contraction value is close to the origin of the axes, close to the average profile. In fact, studying the absolute contribution the level *0.15* contributes the most to the first dimension while *0.17* does the same for the second.

Conclusions:

With this thesis, I described the georeferenced datasets that can be used for the description of land cover and use, explaining the main functionality of each type of data.

I then illustrated how it is possible to use this type of administrative sources for statistical analysis by developing a procedure for the data preparation. These data, in fact, are not meant for research purposes, so their direct use is not feasible without addressing the topological and geometric problems.

In addition to the errors formed in the generation process, these data also have time, land cover and detail limits, so the joint use of multiple datasets becomes advisable. In fact, their combined use allows to benefit from the advantages of the individual dataset, avoiding their single limitations; for example, the Fascicolo Aziendale can overcome the temporal misalignment (3-years) of the Refresh Layer.

Then, I explained all the problems encountered during the joining process and a possible way of solving them, for example how to avoid the comparison between the different reference and projection systems and the matching between the two types of encodings.

This hybrid layer creates many more possible analyses than the individual layers, both for use and for ground cover thanks to the high detail of both the polygons and the thematic resolution due to the double RF and FA coding. In the use of these layers, the significant figure for the distances has been placed to the decimeter (~ 0.1) while other cartographies, such as Corine Land Cover, use pixels from 25 hectares, losing most of the details.

The great potential of this new dataset is also in the possibility of integration with other georeferenced data sources such as information on chemicals present in water basins provided by ISPRA.

I examined the association between land use and the concentration of a plant protection product (Isoproturon) in the surface waters of the province of Foggia.

This analysis shows how land uses differ from each other in relation to different concentrations. The study carried out is a somewhat simplified approximation of reality as it can be extended to the entire regional surface and not just to the buffer around the survey station.

The study uncovered methodological and data source limitations that can be addressed in future research. First, it would be advisable to improve the detail of the hydrographic basins. Through the identification of the secondary basins and by evaluating the slopes of the soil, it would be possible to study rainwater therefore allowing to trace the path that the chemicals follow. This study of water movement is not available for the Puglia region.

It would also be necessary to investigate the properties of the chemical under study, such as its behavior in the soil, its propensity to move with the rains or the quantity that is purchased by farmers monitored by ISTAT.

Even the data on the stations can be improved, for example by considering not the aggregate data for the whole year but by carrying out the study on the time frame in which the substance should be used.

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Appendix:

Extract from the attribute table of FA for Foggia (Table 6).

Table 6

OID_	object_id	cata_comu	c_occu	c_duso	c_uso	c_qual	area_mq	Shape_Length	Shape_Area
273	279	I641	214	0	47	32	18	30,3	33,8
297	304	I641	214	0	47	34	24164	966,2	43185,1
391	407	I641	157	0	0	0	34	112,0	59,9
404	421	I641	167	8	0	0	32985	1138,2	59196,0
405	422	I641	178	0	0	0	395	328,0	711,3
406	423	I641	183	0	0	0	76	47,8	135,8
407	424	I641	183	14	0	0	3730	424,8	6695,4
408	425	I641	208	0	0	0	733	297,9	1316,2
762	791	I641	214	0	48	37	1024	203,3	1831,6
914	951	I641	214	0	48	32	55	87,0	98,9
947	985	I641	214	0	47	35	122	101,5	218,7
955	993	I641	214	0	47	36	138	211,8	245,2
1008	1047	I641	214	14	47	32	17	33,3	30,7
1036	1075	I641	214	14	47	34	90049	2217,0	161006,5
1071	1110	I641	214	0	49	32	142942	2648,3	256095,5
1254	1303	I641	214	14	48	37	226	97,0	405,5
1279	1328	I641	214	14	49	31	8284	644,0	14821,2
1285	1334	I641	214	14	49	32	1118	408,5	1996,0
1449	1499	I641	214	14	47	36	106	80,3	192,5
1451	1501	I641	214	14	48	32	7099	481,5	12688,6
1509	1559	I641	410	9	0	0	7835	784,9	14074,4
1522	1573	I641	420	0	0	0	28564	1023,5	51044,3
1571	1623	I641	410	0	0	0	7439	488,2	13319,0
1585	1637	I641	410	5	0	0	325	100,8	581,4
1663	1719	I641	226	0	0	0	14	90,3	20,2
1667	1723	I641	226	8	0	0	65750	1545,3	117568,0
1674	1730	I641	336	2	51	44	226	311,0	382,8
1683	1739	I641	336	2	52	44	2305	416,3	4123,9
1689	1745	I641	389	102	53	43	11	91,7	19,5

Extract from the attribute table of GIS Suolo for Foggia (Table 7).

Table 7

OBJECTID *	Shape *	FISC_LUNA	SEZI_CENS	CODI_NAZI	NUME_FOGL	NUME_PART	CODI_SUBA	PROG_POLI	CODI_VARI	AREA_COLT	CATA_COMU	Shape_Length	Shape_Area
1	Polygon	B104	-		3	208	-	2	666	11	B104	56,6	11,4
2	Polygon	B104	-		10	65	-	3	666	9	B104	65,2	8,7
3	Polygon	B104	-		14	25	-	4	666	9	B104	41,1	8,6
4	Polygon	F538	-		8	198	-	2	300	17	F538	67,9	17,3
5	Polygon	I193	-		70	1017	-	2	321	7	I193	59,9	6,8
6	Polygon	I193	-		70	1023	-	3	321	10	I193	55,7	10,1
7	Polygon	B104	-		28	237	-	5	666	36	B104	94,5	35,9
8	Polygon	B104	-		43	75	-	4	650	74	B104	133,1	74,9
9	Polygon	F538	-		4	116	-	1	666	91	F538	341,9	91,5
10	Polygon	D269	-		1	43	-	1	666	475	D269	343,5	477,8
11	Polygon	A015	-		9	143	-	16	300	13	A015	91,1	12,7
12	Polygon	G312	-		9	151	-	2	316	8	G312	43,0	8,1
13	Polygon	F538	-		8	111	-	2	666	16	F538	66,3	16,3
14	Polygon	I193	-		12	361	-	3	666	21	I193	91,6	21,1
15	Polygon	I193	-		23	370	-	8	420	35	I193	118,4	35,1
16	Polygon	F538	-		21	82	-	3	660	14	F538	92,3	13,9
17	Polygon	G312	-		32	249	-	1	660	10	G312	48,9	10,3
18	Polygon	I193	-		25	202	-	2	788	28	I193	108,3	28,3
19	Polygon	I193	-		32	141	-	1	660	524	I193	116,5	527,0
20	Polygon	I193	-		41	152	-	1	321	24	I193	85,3	24,6
21	Polygon	D269	-		14	59	-	10	318	18	D269	75,3	18,3
22	Polygon	I193	-		48	183	-	2	321	711	I193	493,6	715,6
23	Polygon	I193	-		57	139	-	3	420	99	I193	151,7	99,8
24	Polygon	B104	-		1	1	-	1	638	38221	B104	1084,3	38456,0
25	Polygon	B104	-		1	2	-	1	638	4805	B104	339,1	4834,1
26	Polygon	B104	-		1	3	-	1	786	584	B104	311,5	587,6
27	Polygon	B104	-		1	3	-	2	786	2026	B104	1023,8	2038,3
28	Polygon	B104	-		1	3	-	3	690	89	B104	78,9	89,7
29	Polygon	B104	-		1	3	-	4	666	59760	B104	1278,4	60127,0

Extract from the attribute table of Refresh for Foggia (Table 7).

Table 8

OID_	object_id	codi_regi	deno_regi	sigl_prov	codi_prco	deno_comu	cata_comu	codi_vari	Shape_Length	Shape_Area
6505	6505	16	Puglia	FG	71009	Candela	B584	330	414,7	8939,5
6552	6552	16	Puglia	FG	71009	Candela	B584	335	375,1	8632,2
8247	8247	16	Puglia	FG	71033	Monte Sant'Angelo	F631	301	16,1	12,4
8468	8468	16	Puglia	FG	71033	Monte Sant'Angelo	F631	309	2995,5	137870,8
8493	8493	16	Puglia	FG	71033	Monte Sant'Angelo	F631	312	2493,9	271268,9
11956	11956	16	Puglia	FG	71033	Monte Sant'Angelo	F631	493	144,3	212,0
15143	15143	16	Puglia	FG	71035	Orsara di Puglia	G125	344	284,2	1671,0
15523	15523	16	Puglia	FG	71035	Orsara di Puglia	G125	359	2603,6	131546,3
18406	18406	16	Puglia	FG	71013	Casalnuovo Monterotaro	B904	138	257,9	4011,5
21589	21589	16	Puglia	FG	71049	San Nicandro Garganico	I054	331	197,2	1125,9
21609	21609	16	Puglia	FG	71049	San Nicandro Garganico	I054	336	223,9	1515,3
27542	27542	16	Puglia	FG	71017	Castelnuovo della Daunia	C222	418	770,6	18423,8
29707	29707	16	Puglia	FG	71031	Mattinata	F059	322	1987,0	30063,2
31679	31679	16	Puglia	FG	71018	Celenza Valfortore	C429	313	2449,4	67587,8
34692	34692	16	Puglia	FG	71001	Accadia	A015	669	1473,6	35015,1
39570	39570	16	Puglia	FG	71044	Roseto Valfortore	H568	343	448,0	4362,3
39621	39621	16	Puglia	FG	71044	Roseto Valfortore	H568	352	153,7	719,1
51048	51048	16	Puglia	FG	71024	Foggia	D643	323	37684,2	844154,6
51439	51439	16	Puglia	FG	71024	Foggia	D643	332	987,7	55234,6
53000	53000	16	Puglia	FG	71024	Foggia	D643	417	1124,8	3862,0
60428	60428	16	Puglia	FG	71002	Alberona	A150	365	2007,0	5324,7
91796	91796	16	Puglia	FG	71054	Stornara	I962	490	1086,5	29837,7
93037	93037	16	Puglia	FG	71055	Stornarella	I963	495	485,5	6764,8
101678	101678	16	Puglia	FG	71029	Manfredonia	E885	334	841,5	41857,3
102880	102880	16	Puglia	FG	71029	Manfredonia	E885	366	58,3	175,7
110591	110591	16	Puglia	FG	71061	Volturara Appula	M131	310	187,6	289,3
183665	183665	16	Puglia	FG	71028	Lucera	E716	681	481,0	8874,1
194201	194201	16	Puglia	FG	71008	Cagnano Varano	B357	492	1433,5	56191,8
195708	195708	16	Puglia	FG	71008	Cagnano Varano	B357	787	543,1	1086,3

Extract from the matching codes and description between GIS Suolo and FA table (Table 7).

Table 9

CODI_VARI	Descrizione vari	c_occu	desc_occu	c_duso	desc_duso	c_uso	desc_uso	c_qual	desc_qual	ok
484	ACTINIDIA	831	ACTINIDIA (KIWI)	0	-	0	-	0	-	1
323	Aeroporti	660	MANUFATTI	0	-	0	-	0	-	1
431	AGRUMI - ARANCIO	201	ARANCIO	0	-	0	-	0	-	1
434	AGRUMI - CLEMENTINE	203	MANDARANCIO (CLEMENTINO)	0	-	0	-	0	-	1
436	AGRUMI - LIMONE	204	LIMONE	0	-	0	-	0	-	1
430	AGRUMI NON SPECIFICATI	430	AGRUMI	0	-	0	-	0	-	1
783	ALBERI IN FILARE	783	ALBERI IN FILARE	0	-	0	-	0	-	1
793	ALBERI ISOLATI	793	ALBERI ISOLATI	0	-	0	-	0	-	1
481	ALBICOCCO	671	ALBICOCCO	0	-	0	-	0	-	1
20	ALTRI CEREALI DEPAUPERANTI (A PAGLIA)	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	1
90	ALTRI ORTAGGI	113	AGLIO	7	DA ORTO	0	-	0	-	1
184	ANETO	221	ANETO	0	-	0	-	0	-	1
655	ARBORETO CONSOCIABILE	430	AGRUMI	0	-	0	-	0	-	1
685	ARBORETO PROMISCUO	430	AGRUMI	0	-	0	-	0	-	1
313	Arboricoltura da legno (noci, ciliegi, ...)	650	BOSCO	0	-	0	-	10	ARBUSTETO	1
500	ARBORICOLTURA DA LEGNO NON SPECIFICATA -	500	ARBORICOLTURA	4	DA LEGNO	0	-	0	-	1
417	AREA DI SERVIZIO AL VIGNETO	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	1
779	AREA DI SERVIZIO ASSERVITA ALLA COLTURA DEL RISO	660	MANUFATTI	0	-	0	-	0	-	1
770	AREA NON PASCOLABILE	506	ROCCIA	0	-	0	-	0	-	1
365	Area seminabile	909	CARCIOFO	7	DA ORTO	50	ANNUALE - NON PERMANENTE	0	-	1
357	Aree a pascolo naturale e praterie	650	BOSCO	0	-	0	-	0	-	1
303	Aree a vegetazione boschiva ed arbustiva in evol.	533	AVENA	2	DA FORAGGIO	0	-	22	ENERGETICO	1
363	Aree a vegetazione sclerofilla - macchia mediterranea	650	BOSCO	0	-	0	-	0	-	1
341	Aree con vegetazione rada	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	1
324	Aree estrattive	660	MANUFATTI	0	-	0	-	0	-	1
782	Aree incolte a vegetazione erbacea spontanea	800	ERBAIO	2	DA FORAGGIO	50	ANNUALE - NON PERMANENTE	43	DI LEGUMINOSE	1

320	Aree industriali e commerciali	660	MANUFATTI	0	-	0	-	0	-	1
322	Aree portuali	660	MANUFATTI	0	-	0	-	0	-	1

Software:

For the CA I have used RStudio Version 1.1.453

```
library(ca)
```

```
point_basin <- read.csv2("C:/Users/pietr/Desktop/Puglia/FG/Point_basin.csv")
```

```
attach(point_basin)
```

```
tabella<-as.matrix(table(GIS_Hyb_csv_Concat,RASTERVALU))
```

```
write.csv(x,"point_basin_freq.csv")
```

```
x<-read.csv("point_basin_freq.csv", header = TRUE)
```

```
dim(x)
```

```
r<-dim(x)[1]
```

```
c<-dim(x)[2]-1
```

```
dati<-data.frame(uso_suolo=rep(x[,1],c),
                 concentrazione=rep(c("0.03","0.05","0.1","0.15","0.17","0.2"),each=r),
                 freq=c(x[,2],x[,3],x[,4],x[,5],x[,6],x[,7]))
```

```
dati
```

```
write.csv(dati,"dati_basin_extended.csv")
```

```
dati_aggregati<-read.csv("dati_basin_extended_aggr.csv",header = T,sep=";" )
```

```
dats<-
```

```
data.frame(codi_conc_aggr=dati_aggregati[,10],conc=dati_aggregati[,2],freq=dati_aggregati[,3])
```

```
dats <- dats[!dats$codi_conc_aggr == "", ]
```

```
n<-xtabs(freq~ codi_conc_aggr+conc,data=dats, drop.unused.levels = T)
```

```
n
```

```
summary(n)
```

```
ca.n<-ca(n)
```

```
summary(ca.n)
```

```
plot(ca.n)
```